

Frequency-Selective Surface-Based Composite Radar Absorbing Structures Using Transferred Laser-Induced Graphene on Glass Fiber Fabric with Enhanced Interlaminar Shear Strength

Introduction

Frequency-selective surface-based radar absorbing structures (FSS-RAS) fabricated in traditional manner involves dispersing conductive fillers in polymer matrix and using metal masks for bar-coating or screen-printing on dielectric substrates. This study investigates an **alternative technique** of FSS-RAS that uses **laser-induced graphene (LIG)** periodic patterns with controllable sheet resistance engraved on polyimide (PI) precursor, **transferred** onto **glass fiber (GF)** dielectric fabric. We successfully designed and fabricated RAS using frequency-selective Jerusalem cross LIG pattern. The resulting structure, with a thickness of 2.91 mm, demonstrates 90% radar signal absorption across X-band. Additionally, short-beam shear tests revealed that **interlaminar shear strength (ILSS)** of the composite RAS can be **enhanced** when LIG layers are integrated between glass fiber fabric laminates. This study not only visualize a new type of wideband composite RAS with LIGs but also demonstrates a **straight-forward scalable fabrication process** including a series of LIG deposition and transferring.

Experiment

- LIG was patterned on PI film using a CO₂ laser.
- Transferred onto glass fabric to avoid PI-related delamination.
- Composite RAS fabricated via vacuum-bagging process.

Results & Discussion

Characterization

- Sheet resistance of LIG evolved through each fabrication step.
- Process-dependent resistance changes were observed.
- LIG flakes and mountain-valley surface morphology identified.
- Raman spectra confirmed LIG formation.
- LIG interlayer embedded between glass fiber yarns.

Microwave Absorption at X-band

- FSS-RAS shows >90% absorption over target bandwidth
- The fabricated RAS cover wide bandwidth, while remain thin (2.91mm) compared with existing literatures

Interlaminar-Shear Strength (ILSS)

- For the [GF₂/LIG] specimens, delamination occurred only at the interfaces without LIGs, while the interfaces containing LIGs remained intact, even after fiber breakage.
- The ILSS values for [GF] and [GF₂/LIG] are similar, while [GF₁/LIG] shows a distinct increase in ILSS.

Design & Fabricated Samples Comparison

- Optimized RAS parameters:
 $p = 8.6mm, l_1 = 1.8mm, l_2 = 4mm, w_1 = 1.2mm, w_2 = 3.5mm,$
 $t_{GFRP} = 0.2675mm$

Conclusions

- Introduced a method for composite FSS-RAS fabrication based on a new type of "porous nano-materials (LIGs)" deposited PI film
- We successfully fabricated broadband composite FSS-RAS with Jerusalem-cross pattern thin thickness capable of absorbing 90% of EM waves
- We showed that ILSS could be enhanced by embedding LIGs in between layers of glass fabric

References

- Lin, J., Z. Peng, Y. Liu, F. Ruiz-Zepeda, R. Ye, E. L. G. Samuel, M. J. Yacaman, B. I. Yakobson and J. M. Tour (2014). "Laser-induced porous graphene films from commercial polymers." Nat Commun 5(1): 5714.

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